

TRANSFORMATION OF GENDER EQUALITY

IN THE REPUBLIC OF KAZAKHSTAN

IN THE CONTEXT OF THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC

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It is well known that gender inequality is a barrier to establishing a real balance in modern society since they contain images and purposes of representatives of different sexes, common in a particular period of the historical development of society.

Gender equality is recognized as an important indicator and necessary condition for the sustainable development of the country, which affects the image of the state in the international community.

During the years of independence of Kazakhstan, certain successes have been achieved in ensuring the implementation of not only equal rights given by the Constitution, but also equal opportunities for women and men, their equal participation in all spheres of life and activities of society. “We have created a solid legal framework, led by the Concept of Family and Gender Policy until 2030. Last month, I signed a Decree on further measures in the field of human rights, one of the main directions of which is gender equality. Kazakhstan is also promoting gender issues as a foreign policy priority in the regional dimension” stated President Kassym-Jomart Tokayev [1].

The modern development of society has put mankind before the problem of understanding the problems associated with the development of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The COVID-19 pandemic has had an impact on the nature of relationships in society as a whole, and gender relations in particular: part of the population switches to online mode, some lose their jobs due to the impossibility of changing the work mode, some continue to work in the usual mode, facing the risk of infection. Taking into account traditional relations in society, the definition of the image of a woman as a "keeper of the hearth", women are disproportionately subjected to greater social and economic pressure than men, which exacerbates the previously existing gender inequality in society, and, hence, the habitual, traditional existence of gender stereotypes begin to transform.

The coronavirus outbreak is exacerbating existing inequalities for women and girls in everything from health and the economy to security and social protection.

Highlighting the impact of COVID-19 on gender, the Office of the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights stated that "targeted action is needed to address the disproportionate impact of the crisis on women and girls." "Clearly, we must fight the virus for all of humanity, with a focus on people, especially the most affected: women, older persons, youth, low-wage workers, small and medium enterprises, the informal sector and vulnerable groups.," said the Secretary-General António Guterres [2].

According to a UN study, on average 81% of women and 59% of men in Kazakhstan spend a lot of time doing housework during the pandemic. In addition, more women work from home in Kazakhstan. About 26% of women and 22% of men in the country have lost their jobs [3].

As history teaches and proves the political experience of a number of countries striving to achieve gender parity and transform integrated actions aimed at strengthening equality between the sexes into all political strategies and socially significant programs, it is impossible to achieve the goals of equality without the participation of women and taking into account their interests.

The overdue major socio-political problem associated with the transformation of gender stereotypes in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, and hence the impact of the pandemic on the vector of gender equality as one of the key indicators of the development of society and how highly human rights are valued in this society, requires an adequate system action of executive authorities, science, education, mass media, other subjects of politics and public opinion.

The problem of inequality, which has become even more obvious against the backdrop of quarantine in the world, in the post-COVID period or the corona crisis, as it is also called, will require a systematic approach - and, first of all, the inclusion of women's experience in economic recovery plans. The coronavirus crisis is forcing parents to balance careers with childcare and distance learning, but women often bear the brunt of these responsibilities. The role of women in the country is still traditional, and in most cases, responsibilities in the family are not equally distributed. This has left companies at risk of losing women in leadership positions - both current leaders and future leaders - and missing out on years of painstaking progress towards gender equality. In this regard, it is necessary to take steps to make women's work more sustainable, to minimize gender bias, to develop and implement policies and practical measures to support women - from providing additional paid holidays and homeschooling assistance to psychological assistance, to strengthening communications.

The post-COVID-19 recovery provides an opportunity to rethink the way we think about politics and governance and build a commitment to the well-being of the people at its core. Kazakhstani women have an important role to play in shaping an inclusive and sustainable future, and they must be given the opportunity to contribute to the inclusive recovery process.

It is known that any crisis also carries certain potentialities. In this case, if society and the state invested heavily in creating more flexible and acceptable opportunities to restore gender balance - and there are signs that this is starting

to happen - they can, in particular, create a culture in which women will have equal opportunities with men to realize their potential in the long term.

At the Millennium Summit, held in New York on September 6, 2000, all the Heads of State of the UN members ratified two main documents that determine the development of mankind in the third millennium, and the 21st century was defined as the century of "gender democracy".

Reference list

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2 António Guterres

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3.

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